

COMMUNICATION ORGANIZE IN REACHING UNIVERSAL PRIORITY OF VALUES.

Azimova Dilfuza Usmanovna

Termiz state pedagogical institute
of Primary Education theory teacher

Narzullayeva Mehriniso Jovli qizi
Master of TerDPI

Abstract: In the article today's in the day cross-cultural communication teach and him organize in reaching universal of values priority and importance about in observation done

Base concepts : Pedagogic ethics, objective laws, pedagogical , psychological ideology .

Independent of Uzbekistan power source of our people universal to values is in loyalty . Our people justice , equality , harmony neighborhood and of humanity thin buds centuries more carefully protect is coming We have done this done being increased at work let's see can Uzbekistan update higher this is the purpose traditions again restore them new content dedication , in our land peace and democracy , prosperity , culture , conscience freedom and each one person maturity to find reach for necessary conditions from creating consists of National our values us from what we see ourselves according to high to the peaks take comes out Because national value it's the nation's of the nation face Education in the process communication organize also national in achieving of values place is incomparable . It is the future generation to his mind imbibe to go from pedagogues big work and requires skill .

Psychological in dictionaries communication to the concept two different definition given :

- 1) communication - cooperative activity the need with enforced contact installation and him development process ;
- 2) communication - signs system through of subjects mutually influence .

Communication is education receiver psychological and social development important from the factors one together in action common to the results reach , interpersonal relationships to the road to put and support in order to two or from him more than of people mutually movement Pedagogical communication when you say pedagogue and listeners team in the middle mutually together of action content information exchange , educational - educational effect show and mutually solidarity organize from doing consists of system , methods and qualifications is understood . Teacher this of the process initiator as to the field comes out and him organize is enough and to him leadership does

ANLeontev pedagogical of communication educational and didactic importance grades since , the following thoughts means : active pedagogical communication of the teacher , in general when pedagogical of the team education in the process listeners to know and learning the key and study of activity creative character , listener of the person formation for the most good conditions which creates , in education acceptable has been emotional environment provider , including spiritual psychological of obstacles appear to be prevention receive education receivers in the team socio-psychological processes right to the road put to manage which provides and educational in progress of the teacher own pedagogical skill reasonable use for opportunities which creates important is a tool Pedagogical of communication in the structure the following stages separately separate is displayed :

1. Modeling (to prediction circle) - pedagogical to tasks suitable mutually of action communicative structure to himself special way planning done increase
2. Directly communication organize achieve (communicative attack) - pedagogue initiative own into his hand takes the group speed with to work attraction reach technology .
3. Communication management - applied effect show of methods communicativeness provide (listeners initiative support , listeners initiative to show

organize communication , dialogic communication to the road put , own target real conditions with harmonious way correction .

4. Pedagogical communication styles done being increased pedagogical communication of technology to go and the results analysis to achieve Communication this pedagogical in the structure stages pedagogical in action in practice apply for from the teacher high skill and because it requires experience him own in place application, possibility Create of course to the teacher depends will be An example for, teacher from class before how communication environment to create thinks and from this except unexpected from situations exit both sides account takes

Group with work in the process them more more active to be for teacher communicative to attack pass , the initiative own into his hand receive , communicate more revive can Initiative own into his hand when of course dialogic speech organization not to forget must and such in case of course lesson to the process suitable has been of the methods fruitful use and today's of the day demand from the "Student centered" method using own place to students release "Student-student" communication organize reach it is necessary Of course this in progress teacher supervisor , road pointer being stands Lesson At the end of of course communication the results analysis is also effective the result will give . Communication organize reach in the process universal of values the place is also incomparable . If we do that such as cases given our examples our own national to our values harmonious without , compared without giving if we go this more good will be Students not only foreign state perhaps own our country national values mixed up without foreign in the language mastering they go And this of course they are foreigners with in communication when our national our values about easily information give get possible have will be Uzbekistan on the ground East spiritual of culture important aspects waking up during developed being , this period living creativity al- Khorazmi , al- Kindi , Abu Nasr Farabi , Abu Ali ibn Sina, Abu Rayhan Beruni , Firdavsi , Omar Khayyam , Yusuf Khos Hajib , Ahmed Yassavi , Sheikh

Saadi , Tusi , Mahmud Kashgari , Ahmad Yugnaki , Lutfi , Mirza Ulugbek , Abdurahman Jami , Alisher Navoi such as many of thinkers creative legacies pedagogical thinking in the development of man spiritual and moral in maturity , universal spiritual of values on the rise important stage it has been . They are Eastern manners requirements based on perfect a person educate spiritual basis to create succeeded they were Spiritual culture in the sources before pushed to ideas action make them young to generation to teach and to his mind absorb of the teacher society and in front of the Motherland high is a duty. Man own value spiritual culture in the sources before pushed to ideas action make them young to generation to teach and to his mind absorb of the teacher society and in front of the Motherland high is a duty. Man own value and identity education in their homes education in the process understand starts Education in institutions teacher by mutually communication based on take to go the following features basically in students communication through spiritual culture formation criteria expressed : Spiritual culture development criteria each one of a person interests according to to know , to feel and respect to do national-spiritual culture sources learning , identity to understand need ; a person in his life of labor place right understand humanitarianism , kindness , faith , nationalism values respect Homeland love , loyalty, self interests society , people interests high not to put parents , relatives and another in the environment to people relatively kind , generous to be

Uzbek of the people oral creativity spiritual of development main historical from the roots is one Each of the people oral creativity that's it of the people character , aesthetic taste , spirit , tradition and traditions , aspirations , geographical condition and nature reflection bringer to himself special is considered a mirror . So it is our people heart thick , high intelligence with centuries during created from generation to generation passing bride folklore also study samples important important have Its rich and colorful structural and different forms modern the environment for inexhaustible creative inspiration will give .

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